

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: STANLEY****FIRST NAME: RORY****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Connotation and Frequency (EUCLID 2021, 28-32)
3. Logical Flow (EUCLID 2021, 39)
4. Sources and Zotero (EUCLID 2021, 34) (Zotero)
5. When Not to Cite (EUCLID 2021, 37)
6. Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 44)
7. Corrections to Papers (EUCLID 2021, 65)

INTRODUCTION TO TURABIAN AND ZOTERO

1) SUMMARY

ACA-401D period one provides an overview of the basics for Euclid University writing style, citation, rules of style, and use of templates. The assigned reading is the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack, which outlines the basic requirements for preparing written assignments and outlines how assignments will be reviewed by instructors. The Coursepack is broken into eight chapters covering a range of topics, including academic writing, punctuation, American and British English, plagiarism, and style, and includes some examples of corrections made to papers. The primary objective of the reading is to inform the student of the best means to write a good essay.

The period also includes two videos. The first covers the Microsoft office word Euclid template that each student will need to personalize with the information particular to themselves available for reuse throughout the course of study. The video also covers formatting, footnotes, citation, style, and spelling. The second video provides an overview of how papers will be reviewed by the instructors and the use of track changes and comments to provide guidance.

a) ESSAY WRITING, CONNOTATION AND FREQUENCY, AND LOGICAL FLOW

The most challenging thing when starting any endeavor is the first step. In reality, every major academic or lengthy project includes many “first steps” to get you to the point where you are ready to start. Putting pen to paper is what most would consider getting started. The Coursepack provides three valuable tips to structure your respective writing experience. The three “steps” include maximizing time by starting early, properly defining the question, and creating a plan (EUCLID 2021, 7). Every individual has dealt with the issue of procrastination and its harmful effect on effectively managing time. The planning tool can help not only maximize the time you spend working but also help cut through the ever-looming specter of procrastination.

How you develop a plan is essential and should include some critical components. It should have an answer to the question you are attempting to answer so you will be able to guide your research to find the information you need to support your solution throughout the essay (EUCLID 2021, 9). Each paper should also have a basic structure of an introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction should include a brief overview of the topic being covered to orientate the reader and must answer the question presented with a thesis (EUCLID 2021, 10). As the name suggests, the body is the primary component of a good essay. A good body will support your argument and must clearly articulate your views while providing data and relevant quotes as to why your argument is sound (EUCLID 2021, 10). Lastly, the conclusion must restate the research question's answer and the main points of your argument (EUCLID 2021, 10). It is imperative to remind yourself of these basic rules. In previous academic writing experiences, I will become so engrossed in the research that I will forget some basic tenants to structuring an essay. Even when you complete good research and develop a compelling argument, the flow of the paper could be improved by proper structure.

Another essential factor is retaining consistency in style while recognizing the usage of expressions that may be unfamiliar to specific audiences. It is crucial to maintain language that is politically correct and non-offensive across cultures (EUCLID 2021, 29). Maintaining consistency in style and language enhances the ability of the reader to understand your writing, thus assisting you in communicating your argument with the maximum effect. To assist in this endeavor, “achieving logical flow” is critical to ensuring your audience can follow your points in a consecutive understandable manner. Using section titles to organize your paper is paramount (EUCLID 2021, 39). This will be especially helpful once I transition into the coursework covering different subject matter, much of which I am unfamiliar with, such as renewable technologies or even topics I am more familiar with, including international energy policy or nuclear energy. Regardless, it is necessary, especially as a researcher tackling an unfamiliar topic, that the research is methodically well documented and has a logical flow. This ensures that the writer stays on point and allows easy access to reference and find documents that might have been researched months previously.

b) SOURCES, WHEN NOT TO SITE, AND CHICAGO STYLE

Consistent formatting and style are paramount for writing research papers. For this purpose, individuals have dedicated their time to developing guides for researchers to follow to assist them in using standardized titles, text, footnotes, headings, and citations (EUCLID 2021, 44). Citation is at the core of effective research writing and provides the skeletal structure for any well-reasoned paper. It is the means to tell the reader where your data or information originated from (EUCLID 2021, 34). There are various means to do this, with endnotes, footnotes, or a list of works cited (EUCLID 2021, 35). Citation helps to indicate the original reference but also has many forms of how to do so.

You can include a direct quotation, but you must remember that “[i]f you use it too much, it does not look liked you own research” (EUCLID 2031, 36). The other more broadly used means to communicate ideas that are not your product is paraphrasing. Still, to use this, the writer must ensure that what they write looks substantially different from the original text (EUCLID 2021, 36). Lastly, as important as it is to be sure to cite your sources, you do not need to cite every bit of information. Anything that is considered to be widely known or accepted has perhaps become more difficult to determine as groups the validity of the earth’s spherical nature. That aside, any information that can be found in a wide variety of sources means you will not need to cite it in your research (EUCLID 2021, 37).

c) CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

One more practical means for me to learn is by looking at examples. It clearly illustrates expectations, what to avoid, and how to format. This is especially true for me when taking a course where in-person interactions are not involved. EUCLID is the first program that I have taken that is conducted entirely virtually. Half of the program transitioned to virtual learning for my previous degree due to the pandemic. Even still, we had weekly video courses and ample opportunity to meet in person if we desired. The sample corrections helped me translate between the template afforded to us and what the actual paper should appear.

However, I still have some remaining questions about how liberal we can be in structuring our articles, and some differences there seem to be potential. This is part of the learning process and expectation setting, which is why the first course is dedicated to writing and style. The method for correcting papers is similar to many other classes I have taken; corrections are made via track changes along with comment bubbles to explain to the student how to properly make a change (EUCLID 2021, 66-71). This form of interaction or correction will be beneficial compared to the previous degree program I was involved in. While we did have the opportunity to meet in person to discuss papers, often, the comments I would receive on a paper were included in the document at the very end of the paper and typically were sparse. Text corrections and notes will be constructive as I work on perfecting the style required for a EUCLID student.

2) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack is extremely helpful and has helped familiarize me with the expectations for writing and style. Period one was also a practical introduction to the different programs available to enhance your writing. Zotero and Grammarly are beneficial, and I look forward to learning more about how to use Zotero. I already recognize how helpful Zotero will be for long research assignments and use throughout finishing a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). This will be an iterative learning experience for me to get the exact style down, which I look forward to, but even more so to get into the substantive coursework. I am very excited to advance through this course and start on various topics ranging from international energy policy to nuclear energy.

Starting a new degree can be challenging as you acclimate yourself to an entirely new set of expectations and programs. Fortunately, the online program, templates, and informational documents provided in this period offer a helpful guide and foundation to begin this endeavor successfully.

REFERENCES

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